

UMERC + METS 2024

Duluth, MN

Courtney Beringer

Abstract (500 words)

Poster

Topics: Wave; Device or component design..., Laboratory and open-water exp...

Title: Uncertainty analysis of commonly reported marine hydrokinetic performance metrics

Authors: Courtney Beringer, Bret Bosma, Bryson Robertson

Abstract:

Experimentally based results for common marine hydrokinetic (MHK) metrics such as power generation, capture width, wave-to-wire efficiency, and power take-off (PTO) forces are all subject to uncertainty. These uncertainties are inherent due to the accuracy of the sensors that collect measurements (epistemic or Type B) and also from the repeatability of the experiments (aleatoric or Type A). Understanding the uncertainty of common MHK metrics is important for advancing the technological readiness level of devices and improving confidence in their performance, but relatively little work has been performed in this area. This work aims to identify the major sources of uncertainty and recommend methods to reduce uncertainty in experimental testing of MHK devices.

Nonlinearities in the waves and the MHK system may be a major consideration for uncertainty. In this work, we tested linear and higher-order nonlinear waves in both regular and irregular conditions to understand the effect they may have on commonly reported metrics. This testing was conducted with the Laboratory Upgrade Point Absorber (LUPA) at the O.H. Hinsdale Wave Research Laboratory. LUPA is an open-source, two-body point absorber wave energy converter built by Oregon State University. It has a 1-meter diameter float connected through a belt-driven PTO to a spar with a heave plate. LUPA was moored to the Large Wave Flume and operated with six degrees of freedom to represent a more realistic deployment of a floating WEC. The PTO controls included velocity-dependent damping and positive and negative position-dependent stiffness to maximize power capture and increase the complexity and therefore the applicability of the uncertainty analysis. Additionally, viscous drag and frictional damping were characterized in previous LUPA testing for validation of a WEC-Sim numerical model. To expand on this, the temperature dependency of friction and uncertainty will be explored in this work. Uncertainty analysis is important for rigorous data analysis and communicating findings with confidence; therefore, suggestions will also be given for standards development (e.g., IEC).